

RECYCLING THE FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES: OPTIMUM DECOMPOSITION CONDITIONS AND FIBER FAILURE MECHANISM

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) composites are used in many applications for their excellent strength to weight ratio. However, no effective recycling system of FRP has been established because of the cross-linked structure of thermosetting resin matrix and inorganic reinforcement fibers. A recycling system was developed for the treatment of FRP by superheated steam. The process was shown to be robust, coping with scrap of FRP and providing useful outputs in the form of recovered fibers and resin. In this study, FRP was decomposed in a chamber. Fibers were collected at purities of up to 80%. The tensile strength of recycled fibers was reduced by up to 50% although this depended on the temperature and time of treatment. Resin was separated from the gas stream by cooling it to liquefaction temperature of resin. The objective of the present study is to investigate the effect of pyrolysis time and temperature on the mechanics properties of recycled fiber and, according to the result of tensile strength measurements, reveal the optimum decomposition conditions for FRP by superheated stream. In this research, FRP was efficiently depolymerized and reinforced fiber was separated from resin by superheated stream. Tensile strength measurements of fibrous recyclates were made and compared to virgin fiber. In the pyrolysis process, some char residue from the polymer remains on the fibers, degrees of char on the recycled fibers was deeply surveyed by scanning electron microscope.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites, which are formed from two or more distinct materials, have desirable combinations of properties that aren't found in the individual components. For example, FRP composites are engineered structures that commonly comprise a soft matrix, typically a polymer, encapsulating a stiffer, load-bearing filler in the form of fibers or particles. For high-strength composites, the fibers should be stiff and have a high aspect ratio (length-to-width ratio). This allows a good transfer of load from the matrix to the filler when the composite is put under mechanical stress.

As the characteristic referenced above, composite materials have been widely used in various industry fields, such as aerospace industry, automotive industry, marine industry and wind energy industry, due to their interesting combination of properties, strength, durability, high strength-to-weight ratios, heat resistance and corrosion resistance. Global use of composite materials had grown rapidly from 158,800 tonnes in 1960 to 6.1 million tonnes in 2004. Today, it is hard to find an industry in which composite materials are not used. But problem is bound to arise as the demand for recycling when composite products reach end of their useful life, especially the composite produced by

thermoset polymer. The cross-link leading to be remoulded difficultly, in contrast to thermoplastics which can easily remelted.

FRP is one of the most difficult materials to separate into elemental components (i.e., fiber, filler, and polymers), resulting in the incineration or landfill of used FRP materials without any recycling efforts for many years. Until recently, a series of environmental legals have established in most developed countries in the world. As a consequence, it is already illegal to landfill FRP in these countries. Environment friendly recycling methods to be established is on the tip of tongue.

A number of recycling technologies have been proposed and developed for thermoset composite materials and these are listed as follows. There are fundamentally three categories of process: those that involve mechanical comminution techniques to reduce the size of the scrap to produce recyclates[1-5]; those that use thermal processes to break the scrap down into materials and energy[6-12]; and those that are based on a reactive medium to decompose polymeric resin into relatively large oligomers while the fibers are subsequently collected[13-20].

Fibrous recyclates obtained by above mentioned technologies were either short or in a fluffy form. The most promising applications for the recovered fibers are those that require short fibres in a disperse form such as in bulk moulding compounds or non-woven veil or tissue products. The longer the recycled fibers are, the orderlier the fibrous recyclates are, the valuable of recycled fibers are. In order to enhance the value of recycled fiber, a new recycling technology, using stream system, was developed.

In our previous studies, it is possible to decompose FRP into reinforced fiber and resin by superheated stream. Superheated stream is steam at a temperature higher than water's boiling point. If saturated steam is heated at a constant pressure, its temperature rises, producing superheated stream. The characteristics of superheated stream are listed as follows: (1) Higher temperature than saturated vapor; (2) Specific volume is larger than saturated vapor; (3) Energy higher than saturated vapor's enthalpy. Superheated stream provides advantages over air-processing mediums including increased heat transfer that may improve thermal degradation and an oxygen-free environment.

In this study, FRP was efficiently degraded and fiber was separated from resin by superheated stream. The influence of pyrolysis temperature and time on the mechanical properties of recycled fiber was investigated. Optimum pyrolysis conditions for FRP by superheated stream was revealed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Manufacturing of virgin fiber reinforced polymer

Commercially available PAN-based T300 carbon fiber fabrics used in the present study were produced by Toray Industries Inc. Epoxy resin were obtained from Nagase ChemteX Corporation, Japan, respectively. Epoxy resin/ hardener were 100 and 27 parts by weight, respectively. The prepreg that was fabricated by Vacuum-Aided Resin-Transfer Molding (VARTM), and these materials are listed in Table 1. The FRP was cut into scrap (50×200 mm) after hardening.

Resin	Epoxy resin XNR6815 (Nagase ChemteX, Japan)
Fiber	Cloth carbon fiber fabrics (Toray, Japan)
Hardener	XNH6815 (Nagase ChemteX, Japan)

Table 1 Raw materials for specimens

2.2 Pyrolysis by superheated stream

Fiber reinforced polymer samples were fed into the chamber. In the chamber, the FRP is heated in the absence of oxygen and kept at different temperatures for a predetermined time, or at a predetermined temperature for different amounts of time, in superheated stream. An instrument with

superheated stream is depicted in Fig. 1. After the experiment, samples were cooled to room temperature.

Figure1. Superheated stream system

2.3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Samples of recycled and virgin fibres were analysed using a Hitachi S-3000N to determine the morphology and diameter of the fibres as well as visual signs of residual resin impurities. Fibers were mounted on carbon discs and gold coated to a thickness of 13Å. The microscope was then operated in high vacuum mode and images were obtained using a secondary electron detector.

2.4 Mechanical strength test

The tensile strength of recycled fiber was determined according to the standard method JIS 11569. The test machine, Auto Graph (AG-20KND) which manufactured by Shimadzu Corporation, fitted with a load cell (SFL-20KNAG) and a linear variable displacement transducer with a resolution of 1 µm was used.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the pyrolysis process, the FRP was heated in the absence of oxygen. In these conditions, resin breaks down into lower molecular weight organic substances (gases) and there is also a solid carbon char product. The recycled fibers are orderly and that has the potential to be used as a feedstock for further FRP processing.

3.1 Surface morphology

The reclaimed fibers were analyzed by SEM. All the SEM micrographs of the reclaimed fibers in Fig. 2 were from CFRP (left column, reclaimed fibers at low magnification; right column, close-up view of a single fiber at high magnification). In low magnification micrographs, we were able to observe the char that remained on fibers. In high magnification micrographs, we were able to scrutinize the damage of fibers.

Figure 2 SEM micrographs of recycled CFs from pyrolysis of CFRPs under different decomposition conditions: (a) reclaimed at 340°C for 15min, (b) reclaimed at 340°C for 30min, (c) reclaimed at 390°C for 30min, (d) reclaimed at 440°C for 30min, (e) reclaimed at 340°C for 60min, (f) reclaimed 340°C for 90min

In the low magnification micrographs of Fig. 2 (a), Fig. 2 (b), more char impurities remained on the fiber's surface after the superheated steam treatment than on virgin fibers (Fig.3). In the low magnification micrographs of Fig. 2 (c), Fig. 2 (d), Fig. 2 (e), Fig.2 (f), the fiber's surface is almost char-free. Under conditions of the same pyrolysis times and different pyrolysis temperature (low magnification micrographs of Fig. 2 (b), Fig. 2 (c) and Fig. 2 (d)), there are more char impurities could be observed in Fig. 2 (b), however, the fiber's surface is almost char-free in Fig. 2 (c) and Fig. 2 (d). It indicated that char impurities would decrease with a rise of temperature. Under conditions of the same pyrolysis temperature and different pyrolysis times (low magnification micrographs of Fig. 2 (a), Fig. 2 (b), Fig. 2 (e) and Fig. 2 (f)), there were more char impurities remained on fibers in the micrographs of Fig. 2 (a) and Fig. 2 (b) than that of Fig. 2 (e) and Fig. 2 (f). It could be considered that char impurities were reduced with the increase in pyrolysis time. To sum up the above mentioned, temperature and time may be crucial parameters which influence on pyrolysis. In addition, no physical

damage (e.g., fissures or cracks) or morphological changes (e.g., in diameter or surface roughness) were observed in all SEM micrographs of 5000 \times .

Figure3 SEM micrographs of virgin carbon fiber at (a) 1000 \times , (b) 5000 \times magnification

3.2 Mechanical properties of the recycled fibers

Studying on the mechanical behavior of recycled carbon fibers is valuable to validate the recycling processes and to identify major weaknesses in the recyclates. It's essential to investigate mechanical property in-depth. Understanding the relationships between pyrolysis conditions, mechanical properties and pyrolysis mechanisms of CFRP provides information to analyze optimal pyrolysis point.

Figure 4 plotted the tensile strength vs pyrolysis temperature curve of recycled carbon fibers, which were reclaimed from decomposing CFRP under a constant time (30 min). The horizontal axis represented pyrolysis temperature, and the vertical axis represented tensile strength. Horizontal line is tensile strength of untreated virgin carbon fibers. The strength of recycled carbon fibers is lower than that of the virgin fiber at the temperature of 390 $^{\circ}$ C and 440 $^{\circ}$ C. However the strength of recycled carbon fibers is a little higher than that of virgin carbon fibers at the temperature of 340 $^{\circ}$ C. It could be considered as that an incomplete decomposition occurred at 340 $^{\circ}$ C. Resin cannot be pyrolyzed completely when the temperature is lower than 340 $^{\circ}$ C, and fiber bundles (held together by minimal amounts of residual resin not completely pyrolyzed) increase the tensile strength of the recycled carbon fibers.

Figure4 Tensile strength vs pyrolysis temperature curve of recycled carbon fibers reclaimed by pyrolyzing CFRP for 30 min

4 CONCLUSIONS

The recycling of CFRPs by pyrolysis was investigated in superheated steam for times ranging from 15 to 90min at 340 $^{\circ}$ C, 390 $^{\circ}$ C, and 440 $^{\circ}$ C. Experiments performed in superheated steam provided resin removal efficiencies above 80wt%. Some char residue from the polymer remaining on the fibers may limit reuse options or require further processing for removal. The results of virgin fibers heated in different atmospheres indicate that high temperature and small quantity of oxygen are the main factors affecting the tensile strength of recycled fibers. Therefore, setting the temperature of pyrolysis as low

as possible to obtain high-value recycled fibers is significant. The tensile strength of carbon fibers is near that of virgin fibers under optimal conditions, and this result is promising. The optimal pyrolysis conditions for GFRP and CFRP were determined. In this research, the optimal condition of GFRP was 370 °C and 30min. Under optimal condition, strength of recycled fiber dropped slightly. The reason why strength of fiber recycled under optimal pyrolysis conditions didn't reduce could be attributed to the resin which wrapped up the fiber that protected from high temperature and small quantity of oxygen.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Pimenta and S.T. Pinho, Recycling carbon fibre reinforced polymers for structural applications: technology review and market outlook, *Waste Management* **31**, 2011, pp. 378-392
- [2] J. Scheirs, Polymer recycling—science technology and applications. London: Wiley; 1998.
- [3] J.Palmer , O.R. Ghita, L. Savage and K.E. Evans, Successful closed-loop recycling of thermoset composites. *Composites Part A* **40**, 2009, pp.490-498
- [4] P. Asokan, M. Osmani and A.D.F. Price, Improvement of the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced plastic waste powder filled concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, **24**, 2010, pp. 448-460
- [5] P. Asokan, M. Osmani and A.D.F. Price, Assessing the recycling potential of glass fibre reinforced plastic waste in concrete and cement composites. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, **17** 2009, pp. 821-829
- [6] A.M. Cunliffe and P.T. Williams, Characterisation of products from the recycling of glass fibre reinforced polyester waste by pyrolysis. *Fuel*, **82**, 2003, pp. 2223-2230
- [7] A. Torres, I. de Marco, B.M. Caballero, M.F. Laresgoiti, J.A. Legarreta, M.A. Cabrero, et al. Recycling by pyrolysis of thermoset composites: characteristics of the liquid and gaseous fuels obtained. *Fuel*, **79**, 2000, pp. 897-902
- [8] L.O. Meyer, K. Schulte and E. Grove-Nielsen, CFRP-recycling following a pyrolysis route: process optimization and potentials. *Journal of Composite Materials*, **43**, 2009, pp. 1121-1132
- [9] K. Ushikoshi, N. Komatsu and M. Sugino, Recycling of CFRP by pyrolysis method. *Journal of the Society of Materials Science*, **44** 1995, pp. 428-431.
- [10] B.J. Jody, J.A. Pomykala, E.J. Daniels and J.L. Greminger, A process to recover carbon fibers from polymer-matrix composites in end-of-life vehicles. *JOM*, **56**, 2004, pp. 43-47
- [11] S.J. Pickering, R.M. Kelly, J.R. Kennerley and C.D. Rudd. A fluidised bed process for the recovery of glass fibres from scrap thermoset composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, **60**, 2000, pp.509-523.
- [12] S.J. Pickering, Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials - current status. *Composites Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 1206-1215.
- [13] A. Horide, Recycling technique of FRP using mixed acid: evaluation of mechanical properties of recycled fiber reinforced plastic. *Proceeding of Symposium on Environmental Engineering*, **15**, 2005, pp.141-144.
- [14] M. Negami, K. Sano, M. Yoshimura and S. Tasaka, Dissolution method of unsaturated polyester in bean oil, *JSAE Review*, **24**, 2003, pp. 221-225.
- [15] T. Iwaya, S. Tokuno, M. Sasaki, M. Goto and K. Shibata, Recycling of fiber reinforced plastics using depolymerization by solvothermal reaction with catalyst. *Journal of Materials Science*, **43**, 2008, pp. 2452-2456
- [16] C.A. Eckert, B.L. Knutson and P.G. Debenedetti, Supercritical fluids as solvents for chemical and materials processing. *Nature*, **383**, 1996, pp. 313-318
- [17] J.R. Hyde, E. Lester, S. Kingman, S. Pickering and K.H. Wong, Supercritical propanol, a possible route to composite carbon fibre recovery: a viability study. *Composites Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp.2171 - 2175
- [18] R. Pinero-Hernanz, C. Dodds, J. Hyde, J. Garcia-Serna, M. Poliakoff, E. Lester, M.J. Cocero, S. Kingman, S. Pickering and K.H. Wong, Chemical recycling of carbon fibre reinforced composites in nearcritical and supercritical water. *Composites Part A*, **39**, 2008, pp. 454-461.

- [19] R. Pinero-Hernanz, J. Garcia-Serna, C. Dodds, J. Hyde, M. Poliakoff, M.J. Cocero, S. Kingman, S. Pickering and E. Lester, Chemical recycling of carbon fibre composites using alcohols under subcritical and supercritical conditions. *Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, **46**, 2008, pp. 83-92.
- [20] G. Jiang , S.J. Pickering, E.H. Lester, T.A. Turner, K.H. Wong and N.A. Warrior, Characterisation of carbon fibres recycled from carbon fibre/epoxy resin composites using supercritical n-propanol. *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 192-198.